

Place Deictic Expression Usage in English Movie “Diary of a Wimpy Kid”

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ABSTRACT: Knowing how the deictic expression is delivered in our daily interaction is way necessary to help participant in avoiding an ambiguity interpretation. This researcher aimed to analyze how speaker and hearer interaction in Diary of a Wimpy Kid dealt with place deictic expression and to reveal the type of place deictic used within each usage by considering some different usage of deictic term proposed by Levinson (1983) and other linguist. This research used descriptive qualitative method to analysis place deictic term found in the Diary of a Wimpy Kid movie. There are four different usage found, they are gestural, symbolic, anaphoric, and non-anaphoric usage. Both gestural and symbolic involve pure and impure place deictic. While anaphoric and non-anaphoric only involve pure and impure for each. Those usage is use differently to convey meaning based on context of utterance that tied to the participant.

KEYWORDS: deixis, deictic expression usage, movie.

INTRODUCTION

Any interaction hardly goes without using deictic expression either in real life or even in a movie as human’s visualization story of life. When a person do asking “what is this?” to their interlocutor, for instance, the word “this” is used to pointing any entity of what the speaker eager to know. That is one example of how language is used to interpret meaning of intention. Study of language usage is known as pragmatic as it remarked by Levinson (1983, p. 5).

In pragmatic study, the use of demonstrative such as in previous example, deals with the study of deixis. Historically, deixis, pronounced [ˈdɪkəsis], is a term derives from Greek, use for pointing and indicating via language. While the term, deictic is known as term used to manifest a deixis use. Levinson (1983, p. 62) categorize the deictic used according its each category. According to him, traditionally deixis categorized as person deixis where the deictic expression used to identifying a person, for example, in English using “I” to identifying first person, “you” for second person, etc.; place deixis where the deictic expression used to identifying a place or location by using demonstrative “this”, “that”, etc.; and time deixis where the deictic expression used to identifying time of utterance, such as “now”, “then” etc.. In other word deictic is a term used to manifest a deixis use. Furthermore, according to Cummins (2023), deixis role in language is pervasive because, in indicating ‘when’, ‘where’, ‘who’, ‘what’ and so on, it is very useful to start with the coordinates of the situation of utterance using deixis.

Deixis as one of pragmatic scopes also copes the same frame which has contextual aspect intertwining between them (Sahib et al., 2021). It is concern on how language is use to convey meaning through the speaker’s utterance based on context. On the use of place deixis for instance, the context that speaker and hearer must pay attention to when using the demonstrative or place adverb in identifying a location is the space around them. In line to this, Yule (1996, p. 8), emphasized that deixis is clearly a form of referring that is tied to the speaker's context, with the most basic distinction between deictic expressions being 'near speaker' versus 'away from speaker'. Therefore, place deixis also known as spatial deixis. According to Cruse (2000, p. 320), spatial deixis manifests itself principally in the form of locative adverbs such as here and there, and demonstratives/determiners such as this and that.

The English word ‘there’ at best encodes a direction “away from the speaker” (Danziger, 2010, p. 178). In contrast, the word “here” encodes a direction “near from the speaker”. This way use of demonstrative and adverb of location in a language is most known as Proximal and Distal (Levinson, 1983, p. 62; Rahman & Letlora, 2018). Manifesting place deixis through place deictic that indicate proximal-distal dimension of distance between object and speaker is usually utilized by using three different ways which called gestural, symbolic, and anaphoric (Yule, 1996, p. 93).

Apart from the different type of usage, place deictic also retain pure and impure place deictic in the types of usage. Previous research about this pure and impure deictic is barely conducted by linguist. Meanwhile the previous research that analyzed how place deictic usage was once done by Spencer et al., (2021) entitle “Donald Trump and His Speech: a Study of Different Usages of Deixis”. The

researchers focused on finding how the usage of deictic expression in consideration to deictic usage by Levinson (1983, p. 65) within Donald Trump's speech at Rose Garden, White House, which delivered on 1 June 2020 as the President of United States. From the speech the researchers found deixis usage of symbolic, gestural, and non-deictic usage.

Another research of deixis used in a movie also came from Hidayat et al., (2021). The researchers was focused to find the deixis that used in "Wonder Women" movie to know the type of the founding deixis. As the result, they categorized the deixis found into five types. They are, first person, second person, third person, discourse deixis and temporal deixis (Sukmawaty et al., 2022; Weda et al., 2021). In discourse deixis, the researchers explained some demonstrative and locative adverb usage, i.e. cataphoric and anaphoric usage. However, discourse deixis (or text) was type of deixis that influence by Lyons (1968); Fillmore, (1975).

This recent research focused on one deixis types originally examined by Levinson (1983), i.e. Place deixis. The researcher eager (1) to analyse how the way of place deictic expression used in the chosen movie was delivered; it is about to analyse whether it used gestural, symbolic or anaphoric way and (2) to know what type of place deictic expression found from the way it is delivered; it is about to know whether it categorized as pure or impure place deictic

LITERATURE REVIEW

Deictic Expression

Deictic expressions are words, phrases and features of grammar that have to be interpreted in relation to the situation in which they are uttered, such as me 'the sender of the utterance' or here 'the place where the sender is' (Griffiths, 2006, p. 14). The use of deictic expression is divided based on each category; for instance, from the example given by Griffiths (2006) above, "me" is one of deictic expression that known as person deixis which also used to identifying second person of participant in a speech event. Meanwhile "here" is one of deictic expression that known as place deixis (Sukmawaty et al., 2022; Sahib et al., 2019)

In addition, Yule (1996, p. 93) said that the most obvious place deictic terms in English are the adverbs "here" and "there" and the demonstratives "this" and "that". The demonstrative is along with the plural form. The adverbs "here" and "there" are often thought of as simple contrasts on a proximal/distal dimension, stretching away from the speaker's location (Levinson, 1983, p. 80). The same in demonstrative, it also to organized in a straightforward proximal-distal dimension, whereby this can mean 'the object in a pragmatically given area close to the speaker's location at CT', and that 'the object beyond the pragmatically given area close to the speaker's location at CT' (Lyons in Levinson, 1983, p. 81). CT is the abbreviation Coding Time give for referring to temporal points and spans relative to the time at which an utterance was spoken (or a written message inscribed).

Furthermore, place deictic is also categorized as pure and impure deixis. Valeika and Verikaitė (2010, p. 20) stated that place deictic expression which involve pure deictic are used independently, i.e. they are not followed by words naming entities, e.g. What is this/that? Meanwhile, impure deictic are deictic followed by words naming the entities, e.g. What is this thing? Who is this man?. In line to this, Levinson (1980, p. 79) also added adverbs here and there as pure place deictic.

Place Deictic Terms' Way to Use

Levinson (1983, p. 64) said that it is essential to distinguish different kinds of usage of deictic expression. Regarding to this, Levinson consider the deictic usage distinguish by Fillmore (1975). There are important distinctions in the uses of adverbs "here" and "there" and the demonstratives "this" and "that" and other deictic words can be used in one or more of three different ways which called gestural, symbolic, and anaphoric (Fillmore in Yule, 1996, p. 93).

Gestural

By the gestural use of a deictic expression meant that use by which it can be properly interpreted only by somebody who is monitoring some physical aspect of the communication situation (Yule, 1996, p. 93). Similarly, Levinson (1983, p. 65) states that gestural usages require a moment by moment physical monitoring of the speech event for their interpretation.

Besides Yule (1996) and Levinson (1983), Cruse (2006, p.74) also gives explanation about gestural deixis. According to him, the term refers to the use of a deictic expression in a situation where, prototypically, speaker and hearer are together and the hearer can see what the speaker is doing. He also added Gestural deixis typically involves a gesture on the part of the speaker. Thus it can be inferred that the use of gestural is the use of deictic expression in a speech moment by someone who is monitoring physical aspect to obtain appropriate interpretation and it could be done when the interlocutor is nearby to be able seeing the monitoring moment.

However, it is important to keep in mind that we have a large range of gestures available (Louwerse & Bangerter, 2005, p. 1). According to Louwerse and Bangerter (2005, p. 1) Generally, there are four categories of gesture are distinguished. Gesture that relate to deictic there are concrete deictic gestures (pointing at a painting when talking about the Rembrandt's Nightwatch), and abstract deictic gestures (gesturing from left to right saying "from the beginning to the end"); Therefore, in analyzing gestural usage, the research will focused on concrete deictic gestures. The following are some examples given for the use place deictic expression by gestural use.

Example:

I want you to put it there (here gestural shows where the speaker is pointing in order to know what place he is indicating) (Yule, 1996, p. 93).

It was this big (speaker indicates a size with his hands) (Cruse, 2006, p.74).

This is totally unacceptable (speaker points to an offensive poster) (Cruse, 2006, p. 74).

This one's genuine, but this one is a fake (here is example of the use of demonstrative with a selecting gesture) (Levinson, 1983, p. 65).

Symbolic

By the symbolic use of a deictic expression meant that use whose interpretation involves merely knowing certain aspects of the speech communication situation (Yule, 1996, p. 93). In line to this, Levinson (1983, p. 65) also stated that symbolic usages of deictic terms require for their interpretation only knowledge of (in particular) the basic spatio-temporal parameters of the speech event. Moreover, Cruse (2006, p. 175) also said that symbolic deixis refers to the use of a deictic expression where close monitoring of the situation by the hearer is not required because the relations between the speaker and the things referred to are relatively stable and do not change over the course of a conversation or discourse. Therefore, symbolic use may be interpreted as the use of deictic expression which its interpretation always depends on the knowledge of the general location of the participants or in other word the parameter that used to interpret this use of deictic expression is relative on the participants' position at the speech moment. Some examples of symbolic use in place deictic expression are as follows.

"Is Johnny there?", (here the symbolic use is exemplified in the telephoner's utterance, where the word there is understood as meaning in the place where addressee are) (Yule, 1996, p. 93). I've lived here all my life (Cruse, 2006, p. 175). This city is really beautiful (Levinson, 1983, p. 65). That's a beautiful view (Levinson, 1983, p. 66). I'm writing to say I'm having a marvellous time here (the symbolic usage of here, as this, can be glossed as the pragmatically given unit of space that includes the location of the speaker at CT (coding time) or at the time of speaking) (Levinson, 1983, p. 79).

Anaphoric

By the anaphoric use of a deictic expression meant that use which can be correctly interpreted by knowing what other portion of the same discourse the expression is co-referential with (Yule, 1996, p. 93). It means to interpret the deictic expression uttered by speaker in a conversation needs to pay attention to the entity mentioned before in the speaking time. This explanation is strengthened by Levinson (1983, p. 67) whose said an anaphoric usage is where some term picks out as referent the same entity (or class of objects) that some prior term in the discourse picked out. The following will be some examples of the use of place deictic expression as anaphoric use.

An example of the anaphoric use of there is in a sentence like "I drove the car to the parking lot and left it there" (in this case the word refers to a place which had been identified earlier in the discourse, namely the parking lot) (Yule, 1996, p. 93).

I was born in London and have lived there ever since (there refers back to whatever place London refers to, but simultaneously contrasts with here on the deictic dimension of space, locating the utterance outside London (Levinson, 1983, p. 67).

In addition, from the three explained above, Levinson also define different usages of deictic term, and added the fourth way to use, called non-anaphoric usage. This usage is categorized as non-deictic usage along with anaphoric usage. Levinson gave an explanation of a non-anaphoric usage from the following example:

How are things there?

The deictic expression "there" from above example does not generally mean 'how are things at some place distant from the speaker', but rather 'how are things where the addressee is'. Other examples from Levinson (1983, p. 66) are as follow.

I met this weird guy the other day.

Oh, I did this and that.

There we go!

METHOD

This research used descriptive qualitative method to analysis place deictic term found in the Diary of a Wimpy Kid movie. The data was collected by watching the chosen movie carefully to analyse how the way of deictic expression that categorized as place deictic is delivered by the actor and actress during the film running. Diary of a Wimpy Kid has some series to analyse, but in this research, apart from the cartoon series, the researcher will focus on the series that released in 2017 entitle Diary of a Wimpy Kid: The Long Haul series. In analysing the data the researcher will transcribe the conversation that retained the use of place deictic expression, mark the duration, and then examined the deictic usage based on Levinson (1983) and Fillmore in Yule (1996). After that the researcher will also categorized the data finding based on its category, whether it is pure or impure.

RESULT

Gestural usage

In gestural use, English use this usage to point to object the speaker want the addressee pay attention to. To join the attention actors and actresses from the movie use any hand gestures and other deictic kinesics action (Enfield, 2001, p. 186), involve hand gesture and gaze toward the object referent. The following are some example of data founding for gestural usage categorized as pure place deictic where the deictic expression is used independently to point to singular or plural entity, so as for location.

NO.	DATA
1.	From 00:35:31 to 00:35:41 Host men : Sorry, missy, you did not guess the exact weight. But... you do get this. Manny : Lollipop.
2.	From 00:09:30 to 00:09:37 Susan : Guys! Guys. This is way too much stuff. Rodrick : These are definitely essentials.
3.	From 01:16:10 to 01:16:17 Mr. Beardo : I'm gonna get you punks! I'm gonna chase you down! Frank : Oh, yeah? Then you're gonna need these.
4.	From : 00:50:44 to 50:50:00 Susan : It's a memory book. Let's see. That's Meemaw when she was baby. Rodrick : Is she a boy or a girl?
5.	From 01:02:13 to 01:02:19 Greg : Oh, no. Mr. Beardo : Yeah, yeah, yeah, put that in.
6.	From 00:26:47 to 00:26:56 Mr. Beardo's Dugther : And he called you a fat Beardo! Mr. Beardo : Come here, punk!
7.	From 00:03:52 to 00:03:56 Greg : Manny, stay there. Manny : Hey, Bubby.

8.	<p>From 00:55:37 to 00:55:58</p> <p>Greg : Look! There he is. Once people see a video of me and Mac Digby, I'll be the coolest kid in middle school, and everyone will forget about Diaper Hands.</p> <p>Rodrick : No one will ever forget about Diaper Hands. It's way too funny.</p>
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From data 1 and 3 in gestural usage for pure deictic, the Host Men and Frank use pure demonstrative “**this**” and “**these**” to refer to **a lollipop** and **some keys** by using gesticulation or hand gesture to show them to Manny and Mr. Beardo; data 2 Rodrick use pure demonstrative “**these**” to refer to **his music stuffs** which meant to be brought to their vacation by using his both hand gestured toward them; data 4 Susan use pure demonstrative “**that**” to refer to **the picture of a person named Meemaw** by touching it; data 5, 6, and 7 Mr. Beardo and Greg use pure demonstrative “**that**”, “**here**” and “**there**” by pointing with index finger, for “**that**” used to point to **a case** that hold by Mr. Beardo’s daughter, for “**here**” Mr. Beardo pointing downward to emphasize **the exact place where Greg have to move**, and the same for “**there**” Greg use pointing to **the place where Manny is** to not move anywhere; and in data 8 Greg use “**there**” while gazing toward **the place where Mac Digby is** to make Rodrick joint his attention.

Next section is shown some examples of data founding for gestural usage categorized as impure place deictic. The impure ones use the same gesture as in pure ones. The way it categorized as impure place deictic is that the following deictic expression used are accompanied or followed by the name of the object referent, to join the attention with gesture.

NO.	DATA
1.	<p>From 00:55:59 to 00:56:06</p> <p>Security : Nuh-uh.</p> <p>Greg : I have an appointment with Mac Digby. He sent me this email inviting me to play with him.</p>
2.	<p>From 00:27:01 to 00:27:07</p> <p>Mr. Beardo: Hey! Is that your kid?</p> <p>Stranger : Huh? What kid?</p>
3.	<p>From 01:01:18 to 01:01:22</p> <p>Frank : What's that idiot honking at?</p> <p>Susan : Just let him get by you.</p>
4.	<p>From 01:02:25 to 01:02:40</p> <p>Susan : Meemaw's book! The memory book is in that case.</p> <p>Frank : Come on!</p>

From data 1 in gestural usage for pure deictic above, Greg use demonstrative “**this**” categorized as impure place deictic because it is followed by the entity name i.e. **an email** while showing it to the security; in data 2 Mr. Beardo use impure demonstrative “**that your kid**” while pointing backward by hand gesture with his thumb toward Greg; and in data 3 and 4 Frank and Susan use hand gesture with index finger to straight pointing to “**that idiot**” meant for person who did honking to him i.e. Mr. Beardo and “**that case**”, while gazing toward it, Susan meant for a case that taken by Mr. Beardo.

Symbolic Usage

For symbolic usages found in the movie, the use require for their interpretation only when speaker and addressee are share the same particular knowledge as the basic spatial parameters at the speech moment. The following examples illustrate the place deictic use by symbolic usage found for pure place deictic.

NO.	DATA
1.	From 00:52:54 to 00:53:01 Rodrick : I've never seen so many dorks in one place before. Greg : These are my people.
2.	From 00:19:46 to 00:20:05 Rodrick : They're for dessert. I got us a microwave pizza. Frank : Rodrick? That's a mini-safe.
3.	From 00:33:44 to 00:34:00 Susan : You guys go get your country on. Spit some seed, ride some hay. And don't forget to eat something healthy, okay? Take advantage of all the amazing produce here. Greg : Definitely, yeah, definitely. Rodrick : Yeah, produce.
4.	From 00:03:12 to 00:03:22 Susan : Oh, no. Manny's stuck. Many : Mommy! Mommy! Susan : Greg, will you go help him? Greg : Why me? Frank : Cause you're the only one who can fit in there.

From data 1, pure demonstrative “**these**” used by Greg symbolically pointing to **people around him** that have the same passion to play game in the place of gaming area where he and hearer are in, i.e. in Player Expo; from data 2 Frank used pure demonstrative “**that**” symbolically pointing to **a mini-safe** that Rodrick thought as a microwave before, here Frank and Rodrick share the same knowledge of what frank refer to since the relation between speaker, hearer and object referent did not change over their conversation; from data 3 Susan used pure demonstrative “**here**” symbolically pointing to the place where she as speaker and his family as hearers are in, i.e. in a carnival; and from data 4, the same as in data 2 Frank used pure demonstrative “**there**” symbolically pointing to the place where Manny stuck in and Greg know where the place meant by Frank since the relation between them and object referent are relative stable. Next section will be the finding and discussion about some examples of data founding for symbolic usage categorized as impure place deictic.

NO.	DATA
1.	From 00:36:36 to 00:36:45 Greg : Oh, no, no, no. We... we can't take this pig. Host men: You're saying that you're not gonna let the little one keep it? A boy needs a pig.
2.	From 00:48:42 to 00:48:55 Greg : Rodrick, I thought Meemaw's was just two inches from Player Expo. But on this map, it's like seven! Rodrick : So? So we're going to be too far away from it.
3.	From 00:59:38 to 00:59:53 Susan: I just wanted to have a nice family trip where we all spent time together, but you don't care about that. Greg : Well, you don't care about the things I love, either! If you did, I wouldn't have had to sneak away to get to this place!

From data 1 Greg impure place deictic “**this**” symbolically referring to **pig** that given to his younger brother which its position is closer to them than toward the hearer, thus without gesture it will not make ambiguity for hearer when interpreting the meaning, also the object referent does not change over their conversation; from data 2 Greg also used impure place deictic “**this**” symbolically referring to the **map** he hold on his hand, or in other word the map is close to him; and from data 3 Greg used impure place deictic

“this” symbolically to pointing to the **place** where Greg and Susan are in, and both know which place meant by greg, i.e. in Player Expo.

Anaphoric usage

By the anaphoric use of a place deictic found from the movie show the same way which to interpret the place deictic that express by the speaker is may only be understood by knowing what other portion of the place deictic is co-referential with. The following examples illustrate the place deictic use by anaphoric usage categorized as pure deictic. Meanwhile for the impure one, the researcher found none of it within the movie by this usage.

No.	DATA
1.	From 00:02:41 to 00:02:49 Greg : Do we have to go? Susan: It's Meemaw's 90th birthday, and everyone's gonna be there. We're gonna see family we haven't seen in years.
2.	From 01:11:41 to 01:11:52 Rodrick: The Beardos. Greg : If those guys are going to a hot tub, they'll be there for hours, trust me.

From data 1 and 2, pure place deictic “**there**” used by Susan and Greg to indicate a place which is co-referential with other portion that mention earlier in the discourse, i.e. in **Meemaw's 90th birthday** party and **a hot tub**.

Non-Anaphoric Usage

For non-anaphoric way of usage, the researcher found one impure place deictic that containing this usage. This finding shows in the following example.

No.	DATA
1.	From 01:07:59 to 01:08:08 Rodrick : One time, I couldn't reach the remote and I had to watch this show where this guy blasted his heater to cool his car down, or something. Frank : I've heard of that.

From data above, it is essential to look back what an anaphoric is, since non-anaphoric is the opposite of anaphoric usage. An anaphoric usage is where some term picks out as referent the same entity (or class of objects) that some prior term in the discourse picked out (Levinson, 1983, p. 67). In addition Yule (1996, p. 22) emphasized that in English, initial reference, or introductory mention, is often indefinite ('a man', 'a woman', 'a cat'). Since Rodrick impure place deictic “this guy” did not have any referent, and that a Non-anaphoric use does not require a referent at all, the researcher assumed this a non-anaphoric use.

CONCLUSION

There are many place deictic used by the actor and actress found from Diary of a Wimpy Kid: The Long Haul movie. All those place deictic retain the deictic usage by symbolic, gestural, anaphoric, and also non-anaphoric. From pure and impure place deictic in gestural usage, speaker use any hand gesture in delivering the place deictic, including the use of kinesics action such as facing or gazing toward the object referent. From pure and impure place deictic in symbolic usage, speaker use it when speaker and hearer share the same knowledge about the entity referent, or in other word they both have the same parameter in interpreting the indicating object in a particular speech event. By anaphoric usage, there is only pure place deictic found that use to point the other portion that mention earlier. Meanwhile for non-anaphoric usage, there is only impure place deictic that could be found. All these different usage is used based on the context that deals with the participant within a speech moment.

REFERENCES

1. Cruse, A. (2000). Meaning in Language. United States: Oxford University Press.
2. Cruse, A. (2006). A Glossary of Semantics and Pragmatics. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

3. Cummins, C. (2023). *An introduction to English semantics and pragmatics*. Edinburgh university press.
4. Danziger, E. (2010). Deixis, gesture, and cognition in spatial frame of reference typology. *Studies in Language. International Journal sponsored by the Foundation "Foundations of Language"*, 34(1), 167-185.
5. Enfield, N. J. (2001). 'Lip-pointing': A discussion of form and function with reference to data from Laos. *Gesture*, 1(2), 185-211. <https://doi.org/10.1075/gest.1.2.06enf>
6. Fillmore, C. J. (1975). Santa Cruz lectures on deixis, 1971 (Vol. 28). Bloomington: Indiana University Linguistics Club.
7. Griffiths, P. (2006). *An Introduction to English Semantics and Pragmatics*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press Ltd.
8. Hidayat, D. N., Rentiana, L. H., Alek, A., & Septiawan, Y. (2021). The Use Of Deixis In Wonder Woman Movie (Penggunaan Deiksis dalam Film Wonder Woman). *Sirok Bastra*, 9(1), 35-44.
9. Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
10. Levinson, J. (1980). What a musical work is. *The Journal of Philosophy*, 77(1), 5-28.
11. Bangerter, A., & Louwerse, M. M. (2005). Focusing attention with deictic gestures and linguistic expressions. *In Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society* (Vol. 27, No. 27).
12. Lyons, J. (1968). *Introduction to theoretical linguistics* (Vol. 510). Cambridge university press.
13. Rahman, F., & Letlora, P. S. (2018). Cultural Preservation: Rediscovering the Endangered Oral Tradition of Maluku (A Case Study on" Kapata" of Central Maluku). *Advances in language and literary studies*, 9(2), 91-97.
14. Sahib, H., Rahman, F., Duli, A., & Asba, A. R. (2019). Customary Forest Conservation through Informal Knowledge System of Ammatowa Community. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 270, No. 1, p. 012042). IOP Publishing.
15. Sahib, H., Hanafiah, W., Aswad, M., Yassi, A. H., & Mashhadi, F. (2021). Syntactic Configuration of Code-Switching between Indonesian and English: Another Perspective on Code-Switching Phenomena. *Education Research International*, 1-10.
16. Spencer, W. R., Jayantini, I. G. A. S. R., & Suastini, N. W. (2021). Donald Trump and His Speech: A Study of Different Usages of Deixis. *Apollo Project*, 10(1), 15-24.
17. Sukmawaty, S., Andini, C., & Rahman, F. F. (2022). The Shift of Honorifics due to The Promotion As A Government Official: Comparative Study. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 5(1), 166-176.
18. Sukmawaty, S., Andini, C., & Rahman, F. F. (2022). The Shift of Honorifics due to The Promotion As A Government Official: Comparative Study. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 5(1), 166-176.
19. Valeika, L., & Verikaitė, D. (2010). *Introductory Course in Linguistic Pragmatics*. Vilnius: Vilnius Pedagogical University.
20. Weda, S., Atmowardoyo, H., Rahman, F., & Sakti, A. E. F. (2021). Linguistic aspects in intercultural communication (IC) practices at a higher education institution in Indonesia. *Eroupean Language Scientific Journal*, 14, 2-6.
21. Yule, G. (1996). *Pragmatics*. New York: Oxford University Press.

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